

Moderation Organization Commitment to The Influence of Servant Leadership on Organizational Citizen Behavior of Hotel Employees in Kuta

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ABSTRACT: Organizational citizenship behavior is the positive behavior of people in an organization, expressed as a willingness to work more than their obligations, consciously and voluntarily. Successful organizations need employees who will perform tasks outside of the workday and are willing to perform tasks not listed in their job description, ultimately improving their performance within the company. This study aims to analyze the moderation of organization commitment on the influence of Servant leadership on the organizational citizen behavior of employees of the Bandha Hotel in Kuta. The subject of this study is an employee of the Bandha Hotel in Kuta. Descriptive measurement and analysis were carried out to obtain an image or portrait of the respondent. The results of the descriptive measurement are then used as a basis for conducting statistical analysis. Data was collected through a questionnaire instrument (Likert scale) that was tested for validity and reliability. Meanwhile, using the incidental sampling technique, the sample was determined to be as many as 75 people. Furthermore, the collected data was analyzed using the simple analysis technique. Servant leadership has a negative and insignificant effect on the organization, citizen behavior, and employee behavior of the Bandha Hotel. Organizational Commitment has a negative and negligible impact on the organizational citizen behavior of the bandha hotel employees. Servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on the organizational citizen behavior of the Bandha Hotel employees. Organizational Commitment can moderate the influence of Servant leadership on the organizational citizen behavior of the Bandha Hotel employees.

KEYWORDS: Servant leadership, Organizational Commitment, organization citizen behavior

INTRODUCTION

Work dynamics in organizations require practical and efficient individuals, both personally and in teams. Organizations need to be supported by productive employees who are active in conveying ideas and highly committed to achieving the organization's vision and mission. The required individual behavior is interpersonal skills that are classified as organizational citizenship behavior. Prabowo & Djastuti (2014) stated that concern for colleagues and a tolerant attitude are needed to create a conducive work atmosphere so that behaviors that encourage organizational progress will be made. Susilawati & Supartha (2020) stated that service companies and services are produced and felt simultaneously. Heider et al. (2015) proposed the definition of organizational citizenship behavior as performance that is supported by an employee's psychological and social environment.

The Bandha Hotel is one of the private companies engaged in the hospitality sector that provides lodging, spa, and restaurant facilities. This hotel is located on Jl. Padma Utara Jl. Raya Legian, Legian, Kuta District, Badung Regency. The Bandha Hotel is strategically located for domestic and foreign tourists during their vacation in Bali. This accommodation is close to the beach. As a company engaged in hospitality services, The Bandha Hotel certainly needs professional employees who provide quality service to guests. The contribution of extra performance and behavior that exceeds the formal demands of the organization can be defined as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), which is an attitude of employee behavior that carried out voluntarily, sincerely, and willingly without having to be ordered and controlled by the company in providing good service (Organ et al., 2006).

According to Laksmi & Simarmata (2015), OCB is a positive behavior in the form of conscious and voluntary willingness shown by individuals as members of the organization. Such voluntary behavior is manifested by working and contributing to the organization more than the formal demands in the organization that support the effective functioning of the organization.

The phenomenon of OCB was carried out with a brief interview with HRD Hotel, which stated that there were several problems with OCB behavior in the housekeeping department. The author was interested in conducting a pre-study on eight people in the housekeeping department. The results of the pre-study show that the average OCB score of employees has not been maximized. OCB, which is displayed in a diverse and not optimal way, especially in the dimensions of conscientiousness, sportsmanship, and civic virtue, can occur as employee reciprocity for what The Bandha Hotel provides. Servant leadership was chosen to overcome OCB problems in this company because there are indications that leaders are reluctant to help employees achieve their full career potential. This phenomenon is also explained when employees get a complaint from a customer, and the leader is unwilling to help handle it,

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leaving it entirely to the employee and tending to blame only the employee. Servant leadership is considered able to improve employee ocb behavior because it will also trigger the reciprocal relationship conveyed in the theory of social exchange. This reciprocal relationship can be attributed to Social Exchange Theory. Social exchange theory in social structure was initiated by Blau (1964). Blau (1964) showed that social relationships are voluntary acts motivated by benefits arising from nurturing interactions with others. The reciprocal rule in the relationship between two people is that when one person shows good behavior towards the other, a psychological imbalance can occur, with the latter feeling obliged to act for the sake of the former. This obligation then leads to the return of favor received until there is a psychological perception of balance in this process of social exchange (Cropanzano & Mitchell 2005). From the perspective of social exchange theory, Fung et al. (2012) state that employees who have been treated well by the organization will provide positive feedback to the organization. Exchanges can occur if employees and organizations are able to give each other something based on trust (Aswin & Rahyuda, 2017). The theory of social exchange can be concluded that when employees have been served by the leadership and given justice in the organization, they will reciprocate. The retaliation from the employee includes a sense of belonging to the organization and OCB's behavior.

Haider et al. (2015) revealed that Servant leadership is one factor that stimulates employees to implement organizational citizenship behavior. The main concept of Servant leadership is prioritizing the employees' welfare. Servant leadership allows leaders and employees to carry out activities that benefit each other within the organization and the wider community. Servant leadership is a selfless leadership style followed by humility, which believes that being a leader is a responsibility to serve the employees who work for them, according to Heider et al. (2015). Leaders with Servant leadership will prioritize the needs of employees and be aware of wanting to serve employees outside to meet the needs of customers and other organization stakeholders (Ja'afaru, 2014). In their research, Baytok & Ergen (2013) proved that Servant leadership has a positive influence on the application of organizational citizenship behavior. The study's results were different (Donia et al., 2016; Howladar & Rahman, 2021) state that Servant leadership has no significant direct influence on organizational citizenship behavior.

Research conducted by Bobbio et al. (2012) stated that there is a positive and significant influence between Servant leadership and Organizational Commitment. Organizational Commitment is a strong attitude in an organization that shows loyalty (Damri & Haryetti 2017). Organizational Commitment is also said to be a strong will to become a member of the organization, a willingness to work as hard as the organization does, and a belief in accepting the organization's values and goals (Luthans, 2006). Employees who commit to work always dedicate all their efforts to carrying out their duties to achieve optimal work results. Servant leadership is indispensable to making followers feel emotionally connected to the organization. Leadership in an organization is a factor that determines the success or failure of an organization (Setiawan, 2019). Servant leadership is a type or model of leadership that is developed to overcome a leadership crisis in the form of a decrease in followers' trust in the example of their leaders (Lamprinou et al., 2021).

According to Lapointe & Vandenberghe (2018), there is a positive influence between Servant leadership and Organizational Commitment. Suppose the interests of employees have been fulfilled by their leaders through the services provided, and the leaders succeed in setting an example for their employees. In that case, organizational Commitment begins to be embedded in the employees. Dumatubun (2018) stated that one of the central values of Servant leadership is equality and fairness, which encourages and supports fair treatment of everyone; these values can affect people's perception to increase their organizational Commitment. Purwanto et al. (2021) said that the factors that drive employee OCB behavior are influenced by several motives, namely Commitment to the organization, where there is a desire to participate well in the organization and be proud to be part of the organization. Organizational Commitment is a psychological construct that characterizes the relationship between members of an organization and its organization and has implications for an individual's decision to continue their membership in the organization (Mathis & Jackson, 2011). The problems that have been described and several previous research results show that there is an inconsistency in the results of the research. So, this research deserves to be re-examined with the title Moderation Organization Commitment on the Influence of Servant Leadership on Organizational Citizen Behavior of Hotel Employees in Kuta.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) was first popularized by Organ (1988) as a behavior that is an individual choice and initiative that is free and not related to the organization's formal reward system but can overall increase the effectiveness of organizational functions. Organizational citizenship behavior can improve group performance because employees will help each other to produce the best. Employees who support each other do not have to ask their boss for help, so the boss can focus on more critical tasks (Haider et al., 2015). It can be concluded that organizational citizenship behavior is a positive behavior of individuals in an organization that is expressed in the form of a willingness to work more than their obligations consciously and voluntarily to improve the progress of organizational performance

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SERVANT LEADERSHIP

Servant leadership is a leader who describes an altruistic personality who supports followers and helps them grow and learn by providing opportunities to experience and improve their material and spiritual conditions (Eva et al., 2019). Servant leadership is considered a leadership style that is very concerned about the growth and dynamics of the lives of his followers and their community (Perdana & Surya, 2017).

Lamprinou et al. (2021) state that Servant leadership is a type or model of leadership that is developed to overcome a leadership crisis in the form of a decrease in followers' trust in the example of their leaders. Servant leadership is usually directly involved in the organization's building and encourages its employees to continue to develop (Septiadi & Adnyani, 2019). A servant leader acts selflessly and seeks to expand a sense of concern for their subordinates (Eva et al., 2019).

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT.

Organizational Commitment is a strong attitude toward being in an organization that shows a person's loyalty (Damri & Haryetti, 2017). A strong will to become a member of the organization, a willingness to work as hard as the organization does, and a belief in accepting the organization's values and goals (Luthans, 2006). Employees who commit to work always dedicate all their efforts to carrying out their duties to achieve optimal work results. According to Hartono & Setiawan (2013), organizational Commitment is described as a strong desire to remain a member of a particular organization, the willingness of employees to exert their abilities to the maximum for the organization, a deep belief and acceptance of organizational goals.

HYPOTHESIS

1. H1 Servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on the organization's citizen behavior of the Bandha Hotel employees.
2. H2 Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on the organization, citizen behavior, and employee behavior of the Bandha Hotel.
3. H3 Servant Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the organization, citizen behavior, and employee behavior of the Bandha Hotel.
4. H4 Organizational commitment to moderate the influence of Servant Leadership on organizational citizen behavior of the Bandha Hotel employees

RESEARCH METHODS

This study was conducted by testing the hypothesis regarding the Effect of burnout and job stress on the cyberloafing behavior of nurses, with job satisfaction as a moderation variable. This research is quantitative because it uses numerical data or numbers as the research data that is analyzed to reach conclusions. The nature of this study is an explanatory study that aims to explain the causal relationship between the variables observed in this study. In this study, the study population is employees of the Bandha Hotel who have worked for more than a year. The sample size for SEM with the maximum likelihood estimation model is 100 – 200 samples (Ghozali, 2004), or as many as five times the number of indicators (5 x 15 indicators = 75 samples). The sampling process or sampling technique is carried out by incidental sampling following the criteria for private hospital nurses in Denpasar.

ANALYSIS RESULTS

Convergent Validity

The results of this study obtained an external loading value above 0.60. Based on Table 2, all indicators reflecting each construction have an outer loading value of > 0.60 and significant at the level of 0.05, so all indicators are valid

Table 1 Outer Loading Value of Estimated Results After Execution

	Organizational Commitment	LEAD*KO	Leadership	OCB
Leadership Commitment Organization *		1,435		
M1	0,910			
M2	0,912			
M3	0,851			
Y1				0,957
Y2				0,957
Y3				0,942

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Y4				0,910
Y5				0,934
x12			0,890	
x13			0,888	
x14			0,862	
x15			0,845	
x16			0,753	
x17			0,870	
x11			0,874	

Source: Data processed in 2024

Based on the results of the data analysis, all indicators have a value above 0.6 and have met the requirements of convergent validity.

Figure 1. Outer Loading Structural Model After Execution

The outer loading value calculation results in Table 1 show that all indicators met the valid conditions based on the concurrent validity criterion, namely the outer loading value > 0.60. These results can be seen in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Validity of Discrimination

Table 3. Discriminant Validity Test

The AVE value of all constructs > 0.50, and the $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ value (which is blocked in yellow) of each construct ranges from 0.860 to 1,000, which is greater than the correlation value, which is between -0.021 to 0.650 so that it meets the valid conditions based on the discriminant validity criteria.

	Organizational Commitment	LEAD*KO	Leadership	OCB
Organizational Commitment	0,891			
LEAD*KOM	-0,452	1,000		
Leadership	0,349	-0,443	0,856	
OCB	-0,073	-0,183	-0,078	0,940

Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha

A measurement can be said to be reliable if the composite reliability and Cronbach alpha have values greater than 0.60 - 0.70. Composite reliability and Cronbach alpha are reliability measures between indicator blocks in the research model.

Table 4. Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha Test

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

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Organizational Commitment	0,872	0,898	0,921	0,795
LEAD*KOM	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000
Leadership	0,940	0,977	0,950	0,732
OCB	0,971	1,091	0,974	0,884

Source: Data processed in 2024

The composite reliability and Cronbach Alpha values of each construct have a value greater than 0.60, so they meet the reliability criteria based on the composite reliability criteria.

Structural Model/Inner Model Evaluation

Structural Model Evaluation (Structural Model/Inner Model) is a measurement to evaluate the accuracy of the model in the overall study, which is formed through several variables along with their indicators.

1) Evaluation of Structural Models Through R-Square (R2)

Table 5. Evaluation of the Inner Structural Model

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Organizational Commitment	0,122	0,110
OCB	0,085	0,047

Source: Data processed, 2024

The R2 value of organizational Commitment is 0.122 based on the Chin criterion (Ghozali, 2021), and the model is included in the weak model criterion. The R2 OCB value of 0.085 is based on the Chin criterion (Ghozali, 2021), then the model is included in the weak model criterion. The R2 value of organizational citizenship behavior is 0.122 based on the Chin criterion (Ghozali, 2021), so the model is included in the weak model criterion, where the interaction of Servant leadership with OCB has a weak influence on OCB of 0.122. Table 5. shows that the cyberloafing R2 value is 0.122 based on the Chin criterion (Ghozali, 2021), then the model is included in the weak model criterion, meaning that the X and M variations are 12.2% for the employee's OCB

Table 6. F SQUARE

	Organizational Commitment	OCB
Organizational Commitment		0,023
LEAD*KO		0,084
Leadership	0,139	0,024
OCB		

Source: Data processed, 2024

Based on the results of the analysis, organizational Commitment has a small influence on OCB of 0.023. Servant Leadership has a small influence on OCB of 0.024. The interaction of Servant Leadership with organizational Commitment had an influence of 0.139. The interaction of Servant Leadership with organizational Commitment had a small influence on the OCB of 0.084.

Path Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

Table 7. Path Analysis and Statistical Testing

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
Organizational Commitment -> OCB	-0,164	-0,124	0,149	1,106	0,269	Rejected
LEAD*KO -> OCB	-0,230	-0,195	0,111	2,085	0,038	Accepted
Leadership -> Organizational Commitment	0,349	0,356	0,122	2,867	0,004	Accepted
Leadership->	-0,167	-0,150	0,126	1,322	0,187	Rejected

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OCB						
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Source: Data processed, 2024

DISCUSSION

1. The influence of Servant Leadership on OCB of The Bandha hotel employees

Providing information that showed a negative and insignificant influence on the OCB of employees, where the path coefficient was shown to be -0.164 with a t -statistic of $1.106 > 1.96$. The results of this test show that Hypothesis 1 (H_1) is rejected. This states that the higher the Servant leadership, the higher the OCB does not necessarily increase the employee's OCB. The results of this study are supported by research (Donia et al., 2016; Howladar & Rahman, 2021), which states that serving leadership does not have a significant direct influence on the citizenship behavior of organizations. The results of this study are not in line with previous research from Ghalavi & Nastiezaie (2020), stating that servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior. Servant leadership can be a role model in employees to have a sense of care for others. Servant leadership tends to motivate its followers to engage in polite and courteous behavior, such as being mindful of the environment and the impact of their actions on others, respecting others' rights to everyday resources, and not complaining about minor issues. The results of this study are also not supported by Amir & Santoso (2019), Elche et al. (2020), Gnakob (2022), and Harisur (2021), who stated that better Servant leadership will lead to higher organizational citizenship behavior. This happens because putting subordinates first in hotel leadership needs to be improved because it has the lowest score of 3.57. The statement mentions that hotel leaders lack priority in meeting the needs of subordinates before taking care of their own needs.

2. The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Organizational Citizenship Behavior

The Bandha hotel employee

Providing information that organizational Commitment shows a negative and insignificant influence on organizational citizenship behavior, the path coefficient shown is -0.167 with t -statistics $1.322 >$ from 1.96 . P value is more than 0.05 . The results of this test show that Hypothesis 2 (H_2) is rejected. The hypothesis test conducted on the influence of organizational Commitment on organizational citizenship behavior in this study, obtained the result that organizational Commitment has a negative and not significant influence on organizational citizenship behavior. Indicators of organizational Commitment are not able to increase the organizational citizenship behavior of the Bandha Hotel employees. The results of this study explain that the higher the organizational Commitment of employees, the lower the organizational citizenship behavior of employees. The Normative Commitment of The Bandha Hotel employees needs attention, seeing that the average score has the lowest score of 3.60. where in the statement I have a sense of loyalty to The Bandha hotel company, where it gives the influence of organizational Commitment is not able to increase the OCB of employees. The results of this study are not in line with previous research from Arumi et al. (2019) stated that organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on OCB. Commitment is an important thing for the organization, when Commitment is formed in the organization, the Commitment will also spread to all people in the organization. The results of this study are also not supported by Purwanto et al. (2021); Grego (2019); Nurjanah et al. (2020) which found a positive and significant influence of organizational commitment to OCB.

3. The influence of Servant leadership on the organizational Commitment of the Bandha hotel employees provides information that Servant leadership shows a positive and significant impact on organizational Commitment, where the path coefficient shown is 0.349 with a t -statistic of $2.867 >$ from 1.96 . The p -value is less than 0.05 . The results of this test show that Hypothesis 3 (H_3) is accepted. This states that the stronger the Servant leadership, the higher the Commitment of the employee organization. Servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on organizational Commitment. The theory of social exchange is the basis for how leaders in companies understand the work behavior of their employees, and this will imply that employees are treated well by the company so that employees have the Commitment to respond with positive behavior through OCB behavior (Newman et al., 2017).

4. Organizational Commitment to moderate the influence of Servant leadership on OCB employees of the Bandha hotel

Providing information that organizational Commitment moderates the influence of Servant leadership on OCB where the path coefficient shown is as large as -2.085 with t -statistics of $2.085 >$ from 1.96 . With a significance of 0.038 less than 0.05 , The results of this test show that Hypothesis 4 (H_4) is accepted. This means that organizational Commitment is able to moderate the influence of Servant leadership on the OCB of the Bandha Hotel employees. The better the Servant Leadership, the higher the organizational Commitment felt by employees, which increases employee organizational citizenship behavior.

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RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

The limitations of this study are as follows: The nature of this research is cross-sectoral, considering that this research is only conducted at one time and is not continuous. This study does not try to compare the perception of the research Object in a continuous period of time so that it can reveal more phenomena in the research. So, this study suggests investigating other antecedents of organizational citizen behavior in a knowledge-intensive context in future research. This study does not take a broader Object, so the study results are a generalization of the respondents' answers used as a sample.

CONCLUSION

- 1 Servant leadership has a negative and insignificant effect on the organization, citizen behavior, and employees of the Bandha Hotel.
- 2 Organizational Commitment has a negative and insignificant effect on the organizational citizen behavior of the Bandha Hotel employees.
- 3 Servant Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the organization, citizen behavior, and employees of the Bandha Hotel.
- 4 Organizational Commitment can moderate the influence of Servant Leadership on the organizational citizen behavior of the Bandha Hotel employees.

SUGGESTION

Suggestions for researchers to further consider the criteria of the subject's working time because, in this study, it is felt that it is still not long to see a person's OCB level. Advice for employees is expected to have a high OCB so that it can improve employee performance and maximize service to hotel guests. Advice to leaders on how to improve leadership behavior so that they can increase employee OCB.

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